

ISic0218

I.Sicily inscription 0218

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

The text is reported in Fazellus' *De Rebus Siculis* (1558) as being in a private house in Termini ('In domo Garfofali'). It was already either unfindable or illegible ('litera abolita') by the time of Gualtherus (1624)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Lost

Physical Description

Fazellus lists this as one of a number of ancient marble tablets to be found in private houses in Termini

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No information is preserved

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. ɔ · Sempronio

2. 7 · L · Primioni ·

3. annorum · XIII ·

Apparatus

Text of Fazellus 1558

Mommsen: [---]Sempronio

Mommsen: ((mulieris)) L Primioni

Gualtherus 1624, Torremuzza 1769, 1784 (ex Gualt.): XVIII

Translation

Commentary

Interpretation of this text (lost) remains extremely problematic. Fazellus is the only authority who may have seen this (it is implied in his account, but not explicit); all subsequent authorities did not. Consequently, subsequent versions of the text posterior to the 1558 edition of Fazellus all appear to be attempts to interpret the text reported in Fazellus. This contains a reversed C prior to Sempronio in line 1; a symbol in the form of the arabic numeral 7 at the beginning of line 2. Other inscriptions from Termini employ a reversed C in a role other than that of the abbreviation for (freedperson of) a woman; however in each case the symbol stands directly before a numeral, and so has reasonably been interpreted to signify 'circiter'; that context does not apply here. Fazellus can be shown, in another surviving text (ISic0146 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0146>]) to have reported such a reversed C correctly, so the transcription here need not be doubted. There is, in turn, no obvious parallel in Fazellus for the use of the symbol '7' (in another text, also lost - ISic0119 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0119>] - a symbol comparable to a '6' is however apparently employed to signify a hedera). What is not clear is how Mommsen arrived at the text which he presents in CIL, in which the reversed C is arbitrarily transposed to the beginning of line 2 and/or substituted for the '7'. It is also noteworthy that in subsequent editions the numeral is variously presented as XIV and in Gualtherus as XVIII (the latter surely an error of transcription from his source). There is also no material basis for the rectangular form within which Gualtherus places the text.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285250

EDR 127464

EDCS 22100139

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